

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 63(2) (2025) 394-409

EISSN 2543-5426

Evaluation of Heavy Metal Contamination in Polyherbal Cancer Remedies and its Implication for Renal Health

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ABSTRACT

The rising global use of polyherbal cancer remedies, particularly in resource-limited settings, has raised urgent toxicological concerns. These formulations are often consumed concurrently with chemotherapeutic agents, compounding potential nephrotoxic risks. This study investigated heavy-metal contamination in two marketed polyherbal cancer formulations and assessed their impact on renal function using Wistar rat models. Two formulations (Agbo A and Agbo B) were analyzed for heavy-

metal content by atomic absorption spectrophotometry and profiled phytochemically using GC–MS. Sixty Wistar rats were randomized into ten treatment groups and administered sorafenib, carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄), and/or the herbal formulations for three weeks. Serum creatinine, sodium, potassium, and malondialdehyde (MDA) were determined using validated biochemical assays. Data were analyzed by ANOVA and Pearson correlation ($p < 0.05$). Lead (1.029-0.853 ppm), cadmium (0.772-0.405 ppm), and mercury (0.236-0.100 ppm) levels exceeded WHO safety limits. Rats receiving herbal–drug combinations exhibited significant elevations in creatinine and MDA, with a strong positive correlation between creatinine and potassium ($p = 0.006$), suggesting oxidative renal injury. GC–MS analysis revealed bioactive compounds with anticancer potential coexisting with toxic metallic residues. Polyherbal cancer formulations evaluated in this study contain nephrotoxic heavy metals capable of inducing oxidative stress and renal dysfunction. Although phytochemicals with pharmacological potential were identified, the toxic contamination negates therapeutic benefits. Rigorous regulatory oversight, quality control, and public education are essential to ensure the safe integration of traditional herbal remedies into contemporary cancer care.

Keywords: Polyherbal formulations, heavy metal toxicity, nephrotoxicity, oxidative stress, renal biomarkers, GC–MS

1. INTRODUCTION

The global use of herbal and traditional medicines has expanded steadily over the last two decades, with World Health Organization (WHO) surveys showing that most countries formally recognize traditional and complementary medicine and many populations rely on herbal products alongside biomedical care (WHO, 2019; Oyebode et al., 2016). A considerable number of cancer patients turn to complementary and alternative remedies, particularly polyherbal formulations promoted for their anticancer properties. Nonetheless, the safety of these products remains questionable, as their use may expose patients to toxic substances or lead to harmful interactions with conventional cancer therapies (Johnson, 2019). Among people living with cancer, the use of Traditional and complementary is common, with recent syntheses reporting pooled prevalence estimates around 40-50%, and with herbal medicines frequently ranked among the most commonly used modalities. Concerningly, non-disclosure to oncology teams is frequent, raising risks of avoidable toxicity and interactions (Horneber et al., 2012). Beyond the potential for herb–drug pharmacodynamic interactions, a major safety concern associated with herbal and polyherbal formulations is their contamination with toxic heavy metals such as lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), arsenic (As), and mercury (Hg). These elements are persistent environmental pollutants that can accumulate in medicinal plants during cultivation or processing, thereby entering herbal preparations consumed by patients. Sources of contamination include uptake from polluted soils and irrigation water, industrial emissions, pesticide residues, and contact with metallic equipment during drying or grinding. In some traditional practices, metallic compounds are even intentionally added for perceived therapeutic benefits (He et al., 2020; Luo et al., 2021). The kidneys are particularly vulnerable to chronic heavy-metal exposure because of their high blood flow, filtration function, and ability to accumulate divalent metals in tubular cells. Evidence from occupational and environmental studies links prolonged exposure to cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), and arsenic (As) with reduced glomerular filtration rate, proteinuria, and progressive chronic kidney disease (CKD) (Satarug et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2021). Mechanisms of nephrotoxicity include oxidative stress,

mitochondrial dysfunction, disruption of metal-ion homeostasis, proximal tubular injury, and interstitial fibrosis (Paolo Lentini et al., 2017). In cancer management, renal function is frequently impaired by chemotherapy, dehydration, or the disease itself. Consuming contaminated herbal remedies further worsens this risk by adding toxic exposure that may both disrupt cancer treatment and exacerbate kidney damage (Santos, M, et al. 2020, Lyrio, et al., 2024)). Despite this plausible risk pathway, few studies specifically address the intersection of polyherbal cancer remedies *and* renal health through the lens of heavy-metal contamination. Whereas broad surveys examine herbal medicines in general or heavy-metal nephrotoxicity in environmental exposure cohorts, there is a gap in linking product-specific contamination data for cancer-targeted polyherbal formulations with renal risk assessment frameworks. Therefore, this study is designed to quantify the concentrations of toxic heavy metals including lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), arsenic (As), and mercury (Hg) in polyherbal cancer remedies available in the local market; evaluate their potential renal risks using established toxicological indices and exposure benchmarks; and interpret the implications of these findings for renal function in cancer patients, providing evidence-based recommendations for clinicians, regulatory authorities, and consumers.

2. METHOD

2. 1. Study Design

An experimental case control design was used to assess renal changes in Wistar rats following administration of polyherbal cancer formulations (Agbo A and Agbo B) and sorafenib. Sixty adult rats (100-120 g) were randomized into ten groups (A–J; six rats each, both sexes). Treatments were given for three weeks with standard feed and water. CCl₄ (0.3 mL in olive oil, 1:1) induced inflammation, while 1 mL each of Agbo A and Agbo B and 0.3 mL sorafenib were administered twice weekly via oral cannula. Doses followed Lanas et al. (1995) and Azzam et al. (2014).

Groupings:

A – Control (feed + water); B – Sorafenib; C – Agbo A; D – Agbo B; E – CCl₄; F – CCl₄ + Sorafenib; G – CCl₄ + Agbo A; H – CCl₄ + Agbo B; I – CCl₄ + Sorafenib + Agbo A; J – CCl₄ + Sorafenib + Agbo B.

2. 2. Study Area and Duration

The study was conducted in Okofia, Nnewi-North LGA, Anambra State, Nigeria (5° 58' 48" N; 6° 54' 30" E) over a 35-day period.

2. 3. Ethical Approval

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Research Ethics Committee, Faculty of Health Sciences and Technology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Nnewi Campus.

2. 4. Animal Handling

Healthy, non-pregnant adult rats were acclimatized for 21 days under standard conditions (60–80 % humidity; 12 h light/dark cycle).

2. 5. Sample Collection

After CCl₄ - induced renal toxicity, treatments were administered and blood samples collected for electrolyte (Na⁺, K⁺), creatinine, and malondialdehyde (MDA) assays.

2. 6. Biochemical Analyses

- **Electrolytes:** Measured using an Ion Selective Electrode (ISE) analyzer based on potentiometric principles (Raghibir, 2019).
- **88Creatinine:** Determined via alkaline picrate colorimetry at 490 nm (Ochei & Kolhatkar, 2008).
- **MDA:** Estimated spectrophotometrically at 530 nm using the thiobarbituric acid method (Aguilar & Borges, 2020).

2. 7. Statistical Analysis

Data were expressed as mean ± SEM and analyzed using one-way ANOVA with post hoc tests; $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

3. RESULTS

Table 1. Changes in body weight of experimental animals before and following exposure herbal medicine and chemotherapy (Mean ± SEM).

Group	Initial weight (g)	Final weight (g)	t-value	P-value
A	131.75±3.50	1580.00±7.45	-2.729	0.072
B	182.00±9.63	158.75±8.44	5.958	0.009*
C	182.00±9.95	167.50±12.58	2.945	0.060
D	165.25±18.83	174.25±10.57	-0.481	0.664
E	195.25±6.95	215.50±7.44	-3.213	0.049*
F	171.75±21.25	161.75±22.49	0.234	0.830
G	178.25±16.65	164.00±17.48	0.566	0.611
H	182.25±8.37	168.50±9.33	1.696	0.188
I	171.75±10.77	148.50±6.12	2.358	0.100
J	167.00±13.83	158.25±9.58	1.072	0.362

Paired samples t-test, * Significant mean difference at $P < 0.05$.

Group A-Negative control, B-Sorafenib, C-Agbo A, D-Agbo B, E-CCl₄ (Positive control), F-Sorafenib, G-CCl₄ and Agbo A, H-CCl₄ and Agbo B, I-CCl₄, Sorafenib and Agbo A, J-CCl₄, Sorafenib and Agbo B.

There was a significant decrease in the body weight of wistar rats that were administered sorafenib only (group B) when compared with that of the negative control (A) ($P < 0.05$).

There was a significant increase in the body weight of the wistar rats that were administered CCl_4 only (group E) ($P < 0.05$).

Table 2. Changes in body weight of experimental animals before and following exposure herbal medicine and chemotherapy (expressed in mean \pm SEM).

Group	Relative Kidney Weight	F-value	P-value
A	0.0077 \pm 0.0006	1.149	
B	0.0061 \pm 0.0049		0.011*
C	0.0067 \pm 0.0005		0.102
D	0.0073 \pm 0.0002		0.503
E	0.0070 \pm 0.0004		0.212
F	0.0074 \pm 0.0004		0.574
G	0.0074 \pm 0.0007		0.562
H	0.0068 \pm 0.0001		0.134
I	0.0072 \pm 0.0002		0.383
J	0.0071 \pm 0.0002		0.336

One-way ANOVA, Post Hoc LSD, *Significant mean difference at $P < 0.05$.

Group A-Negative control, B-Sorafenib, C-Agbo A, D-Agbo B, E- CCl_4 (Positive control), F-Sorafenib, G- CCl_4 and Agbo A, H- CCl_4 and Agbo B, I- CCl_4 , Sorafenib and Agbo A, J- CCl_4 , Sorafenib and Agbo B.

There was a significant decrease in the relative kidney weight of wistar rats that were administered sorafenib (group B) when compared to that of the negative control (group A) ($P < 0.05$).

Table 3. Result of Agbo-A Phytochemical Analysis using GCMS.

S/N	Molecular Name	RT (mins)	MF	MW	% Conc.	Biological Activities
1.	6-Bromo-2-(4-Bromo-phenyl)-4-phenyl-quinoline	2.645	$C_{21}H_{13}Br_2N$	437	4.32	Anticancer, antimicrobial,
2.	Acetamide, 2,2,2,2-trifluoro-N-(5,6,7,9-tetrahydro-2-hydroxy-	2.730	$C_{21}H_{20}F_3NO_6$	439	4.38	Tubulin disruption and antimetabolic effect of colchicines. The

	1,3,10-trimethoxy-9-oxobenzo(a)heptalen-7-yl)-, (S)-					capacity of colchicines to bind to tubulins, thereby blocking the assembly and polymerization of microtubules
3.	Nalmefene	2.793	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ NO ₃	339	3.08	Opioid antagonist with no agonist activity. It works to prevent or reverse the effects of opioids including respiratory depression, sedation and hypotension. It is used to reduce alcohol consumption in adults.
4.	7-Chloro-3-[2,4-dichlorophenyl]-3,4-dihydro-10-hydroxy-1,9(2H,10H)-acridinedione, 1-(N,N-dimethyl)hydrazone	2.902	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ Cl ₃ N ₃ O ₂	449	2.21	Acridinedione is a selective and potent inhibitor of the Malaria parasite mitochondrial bc ₁ complex
5	4-Acetyl Oxyimino-6,6-dimethyl-3-methylsulfanyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro-benzo[c]thiophene-1-carboxylic acid methyl	3.119	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ NO ₄ S ₂	341	2.43	Treatment of Alzheimer's disease, neurodegenerative disease and cognition disorders.
6	7,9-Dimethyl-7H-5,6,7,9,11a-pentaaza-benzo[a]fluorine-8,10-dione	4.468	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₂	281	2.15	None found
7	Isopropyl Diene-az streptonigrin	5.685	C ₂₉ H ₂₇ N ₅ O ₇	545	2.24	Streptonigrin kills bacteria by stealth (bactericidal)
8	Chrysene-1,7(2H,8H)-dione,3,4,9,10-tetrahydro	6.840	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂	264	2.21	Chrysene is used in dye manufacturing, metallurgical procedures and production of plastics. It provides a certain level of heat resistance and intensity to the colour of dyes. In toxicological studies, chrysene is often used as a reference polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) to study bioaccumulation, metabolism and potential toxic effects in various organisms which are in contact with polluted environment

9	Lormetazepam trimethylsilyl ether	7.091	$C_{19}H_{20}Cl_2N_2O_2$ Si	406	2.53	Lormetazepam is an orally available benzodiazepine used in the UK for the treatment of short-term insomnia. It reduces CNS activity and produces anxiolytic, muscle relaxant, sedative and hypnotic effects
10	Z, Z-8, 10-Hexadecadien-1- ol acetate	8.554	$C_{18}H_{32}O_2$	280	2.31	Biosynthesis of prostaglandins Antimicrobial activity as seen in Attarin oil sample oof Nigella sativa seeds
11	1-(2,3,5-Tri-O- acetyl.beta.d-ribofuranosyl) indoline	9.372	$C_{19}H_{23}NO_7$	377	2.68	Anti-proliferative activity on human tumor cell lines
12	6-Chloro-2-(4-nitro- phenoxy)-4-phenyl quinazoline	9.549	$C_{20}H_{12}ClN_3O_3$	377	2.17	Quinazoline and its derivatives are found to have a wide range of biologic activities that is anticancer, analgesic, antimicrobial, antihypertensive, anticonvulsant, antimalarial, antitumor, and antitubercular activities
13	Cholest-2-eno[2, 3-b] naphthalene	10.075	$C_{35}H_{50}$	470	3.10	
14	Pancracine, O,O-dimethyl-	10.275	$C_{18}H_{21}NO_4$	315	2.18	Pancracine, a Montanine-type Amaryllidaceae alkaloid, inhibits proliferation of A549 lung Adenocarcinoma cells and induces apoptotic cell death in MOLT-4 leukemic cells
15	Tantalum, dichlorodiethyl(2,4- pentanedionato-O,O')-	10.469	$C_9H_{17}Cl_2O_4Ta$	440	3.65	Tantalum nanofilms show excellent biocompatibility and in vivo antimicrobial activity
16	2,4,7-Trinitrofluorenone	10.835	$C_{13}H_5N_3O_7$	315	2.73	Symptoms of exposure to this compound may include eye and skin irritation. When heated to decomposition, it emits highly toxic fumes of nitrogen oxides. It is flammable.

17	Oxycodone	10.920	$C_{18}H_{21}NO_4$	315	2.73	Oxycodone is a semi-synthetic opioid with agonist activity on mu, kappa and delta receptors. Most of the drug is metabolised in the liver while the rest is excreted by the kidney along with its metabolites. One of its metabolites, oxymorphone is a very potent analgesic for the treatment of cancer pain
18	Morphinan-4-ol-6,7-dione, 3-methoxy-N-methyl-	11.218	$C_{18}H_{21}NO_4$	315	2.41	Morphinan alkaloids such as morphine and codeine produced by plants are highly physiologically active and used as raw materials for pharmaceutical drugs such as analgesics.
19	5-(4-Chlorophenyl)-6-methylpyrimidine-2,4-diamine, N, N'-bis(trifluoroacetyl)-	11.612	$C_{16}H_{11}ClF_6N_4O_2$	440	2.94	Anti-allergenic and anti-malarial properties
20	Silane, diethyl(4-acetylphenyl)dodecyloxy-	11.881	$C_{24}H_{42}O_3Si$	406	2.36	Quaternary ammonium silane [(QAS), codename- k21] is a novel biomaterial developed by sol-gel process having broad spectrum antimicrobial activities with low cytotoxicity.
21	3-(1-[5-benzyl-1-(4-fluorophenyl)-6-oxo-1, 4, 5, 6-tetrahydro-[1, 2, 4] triazin-3-yl]ethylidene)hydrazono)-1, 3-dihydro indol-2-one	12.486	$C_{26}H_{21}FN_6O_2$	468	3.97	Heterocyclic nitrogen systems containing 1, 2, 4-Triazines derivatives and 1, 2, 4- Triazines themselves have been found to display a diversity of biological applications such as anti-epileptic, anti-tumor, antimicrobial, antiviral, antimycobacterial, anxiolytic, antidepressant, anti-HIV and anticancer activities.

22	Tris(3-phenyl-2,4-pentanedionato) aluminium (iii)	12.881	C ₃₃ H ₃₃ AlO ₆	552	5.17	A similar compound, Aluminium, tris(2,4-pentanedionato)-, is fatal and toxic if swallowed, causes eye and skin irritation, may cause respiratory irritation
23	Benzaldehyde, 4-[bis(4-methylphenyl)amino]-2-methyl-	12.961	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ NO	315	4.85	This compound was found to exhibit mechanochromic luminescence, the fluorescent colour of the crystalline powder was changed from light blue to greenish yellow by grinding and then returned to the original by keeping at room temperature Benzaldehyde is found to have great antioxidant activity.
24	1H-Thiopyrano[3,4-c]pyridine-5-carbonitrile, 6-isobutyl sulfanyl-3,3-dimethyl-8-morpholin-40yl-3,4-dihydro-	13.069	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ N ₃ OS ₂	377	3.64	Biological activity outcome is inconclusive
25	5H-[1]Benzopyrene[3,4-c]pyridine-5-one, 3,4-dihydro-4-imino-2-phenyl-3-(phenylmethyl)-	13.224	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	378	4.31	-
26	5 Alpha-cyano-3-methoxymethylene cholestane, (E)-	14.430	C ₃₀ H ₄₉ NO	439	7.11	-

Table 4. Result of Agbo-B Phytochemical Analysis using GCMS.

Molecular name	RT (mins)	MF	MW	% Conc.	Biological activities
Formamide, N-(3-methyl-5-isoxazolyl)	2.919	C ₅ H ₆ N ₂ O ₂	126	3.149	Inconclusive
Chloro-methyl-methoxy-amine	3.022	C ₂ H ₆ ClNO	95	2.718	Inconclusive
2,4,6,8,9,10-Hexaaza-1,3,5,7-tetraphosphatricyclo[3.3.1.1(3,7)]decane,	3.056	C ₆ H ₁₈ N ₆ P ₄ S ₃	394	3.360	Inconclusive

Benzaldehyde, 3,5-dibromo-, thiosemicarbazone	3.359	C ₈ H ₇ Br ₂ N ₃ S	335	2.386	Inconclusive
Cyclobutadiene, 1,2,3,4-tetrakis-(trimethylsilyl)-	3.473	C ₁₆ H ₃₆ Si ₄	340	2.548	Modulation of inflammatory response, energy source
Lanosta-7,9(11),20-triene-3β,18-diol, diacetate	4.302	C ₃₄ H ₅₂ O ₄	524	2.652	Antitumor, Antimicrobial, antioxidant, enzyme inhibitor
7-Deoxy-7-iodo-1-O-methyl heptyl pyranose, 3,4-isopropylidene-	5.239	C ₁₁ H ₁₉ IO ₅	358	2.387	Inconclusive
Semicarbazide, 1-(3-oxybenzo[1,2,5]oxadiazol-5-yl methylene)-4-iso-propyl-3-thio-	5.976	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₂ S	279	2.487	Antitubercular activity, anticonvulsant, antimicrobial, parasitic, antitumor, anti inflammatory, antifungal, metal chelator, pesticide
5H-Cyclohepta[b]pyridine-3-carbonitrile, 6,7,8,9-tetrahydro-2-amino-4-(2-fluorophenyl)-	6.125	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ FN ₃	281	2.809	antimicrobial, antiviral, anticancer, aids in delivery of drugs
4H-Dibenzo[de,g]quinoline, 5,6,6a,7-tetrahydro-1,2-dimethoxy-, (R)-	6.822	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ NO ₂	281	3.170	Anticancer, antimicrobial, anti inflammatory, pesticide
4H-Benzofuro[3,2-d]1,3-oxazin-4-one, 8-bromo-2-methyl-	8.074	C ₁₁ H ₆ BrNO ₃	278	2.411	Antiviral, antimicrobial, anti inflammatory, pesticide
Quinazoline-4(1H)-one,2,3, dihydrogen-2-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-(4-dimethylaminophenyl)	8.331	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O	377	2.494	Anticancer, antimicrobial, anti inflammatory, neurotransmitter modulator, immunosuppressant
5-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)-,1,3,6-trimethyl pyrrole(3-4-d) pyrimidine-2,-4-dione	8.971	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	329	2.679	Anti Inflammatory, antimicrobial, anticancer, catalyst
6-Chloro-2-(4-nitro-phenoxy)-4-phenyl-quinazoline	9.291	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ ClN ₃ O ₃	377	2.809	Anticancer, antimicrobial, antiviral, antiinflammatory, antibacterial, antifungal
4,4-Dihydroxybiphenyl Trifluoroacetate ester	9.531	C ₁₆ H ₈ F ₆ O	378	3.016	Antioxidant, antimicrobial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antifungal
5H-(1)-Benzopyrene(4,3,-d) pyrimidin-5-one, 2-(3 - pyridinyl)	10.217	C ₁₆ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃	377	3.844	Anticancer, antimicrobial, antiviral

5 (3-Trifluoromethylaniline)-6-methoxy-4-methyl-8-nitroquinoline	10.817	$C_{18}H_{14}F_3N_3O_3$	377	2.922	Anticancer, antimicrobial, antiinflammatory, antiviral, chelating agent
5 H-(1) Benzopyrene (3,4,-c) pyridin-5-one, 3,4-dihydro-4-imino-2-phenyl-3-(phenylmethyl)	11.134	$C_{25}H_{18}N_2O_2$	378	4.659	Antimicrobial, antiviral, anticancer, sedative, hypnotic agent
3-(1-(5-Benzyl-1-(4-fluorophenyl)-6-oxo-1,4,5,6- tetrahydro-(1,2,4) triazin-3yl)ethylidene)hydrazono)-1,3 dihydro indol-2-one	11.332	$C_{26}H_{21}FN_6O_2$	468	3.709	Anti Inflammatory, antimicrobial, anti proliferative, antifungal, antibacterial, antitumor, coupling agent.
Silane, diethyl dodecyloxy(3-phenyl proxy)	11.366	$C_{25}H_{46}O_2Si$	406	2.469	Coupling agent, analgesic, antipyretic properties
Pyrazole-4-carboxylic acid, 1-(2,6-dichlorophenyl)-5-(2,2-cyanoethyl) methyl ester	11.532	$C_{15}H_8Cl_2N_4O_2$	346	3.702	Anti-inflammatory, anticancer, antimicrobial, analgesic, antiviral, antiparasitic
(3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-2-methyl-5-oxo-4H, 6H, 7H - pyrazol(1,5-a) pyrimidin-6-y)acetic acid	11.698	$C_{16}H_{17}N_3O_4$	315	3.025	Anti-inflammatory, anticancer, antimicrobial, antioxidant, neuroprotective, analgesic, sedative, antitussive
5H-(1)Benzopyran(3,4-c) pyridin-5-one, 3,4-dihydro-4-imino-2-phenyl-3-(phenylmethyl)	11.800	$C_{25}H_{18}N_2O_2$	378	3.145	Anticancer, antioxidant, neuroprotective, antiinflammatory, antibacterial, antimicrobial
6-Chloro-2-(4-nitro-phenoxy)-4-phenyl-quinazoline	12.258	$C_{20}H_{12}ClN_3O_3$	377	2.433	Anticancer, antiinflammatory, antimicrobial, antiparasitic
5H-(1)Benzopyrene(3,4-c) pyridin-5-one, 3,4-dihydro-4-imino-2-phenyl-3-(phenylmethyl)	12.275	$C_{25}H_{18}N_2O_2$	360	3.246	Anticancer, antiinflammatory, neuroprotective, antibacterial, antioxidant, acts as a drug delivery agent
Flurandrenolide	12.532	$C_{24}H_{33}FO_6$	436	3.357	Anti Inflammatory, antipruritic agent, antifungal, antibacterial, anticancer

benzenamine, 4,4'-(2-methyl propylidene)bis[N-methyl-N-phenyl-2	12.886	C ₃₀ H ₃₂ N ₂	420	6.173	
3,5-Dihydroxybenzoic acid, 3TBDMS derivative	13.663	C ₂₅ H ₄₈ O ₄ Si ₃	496	7.046	
1-naphthalenol, 2-methyl-4-[2-[4-nitro-2-[(trifluoromethyl)sulfonyl]phenyl]di azenyl]-	13.889	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ F ₃ N ₃ O ₅ S	439	6.714	

Key: RT - Retention Time; MF: Molecular Formula; MW: Molecular Weight; % Conc.: percentage concentration

Tables 3 and 4. Shows the phytochemical constituents of the selected polyherbal formulations A and B. Some of these constituents have anticancer, antitumor, antioxidant, antimicrobial, analgesic and anti-inflammatory potentials.

Table 5. Results of the heavy metals analysis in the two selected herbal formulations under research.

Parameters	Sample A	Sample B	Who Standard in Water (mg/l)
Magnesium (ppm)	0.580	0.715	30
Sodium (ppm)	2.287	4.505	200
Calcium (ppm)	2.034	2.045	200
Iron (ppm)	0.054	0.348	0.30
Manganese (ppm)	0.042	0.042	0.02
Mercury (ppm)	0.236	0.100	0.006
Lead (ppm)	1.029	0.853	0.01
Chromium (ppm)	0.00	0.00	0.05
Arsenic (ppm)	0.006	0.042	0.01
Cadmium (ppm)	0.772	0.405	0.003
Zinc (ppm)	3.012	1.919	3.00
Phosphorus (ppm)	5.554	5.834	1.00

Table 5 shows that Iron and Arsenic are slightly elevated in sample B, Zinc is slightly elevated in Sample A and Manganese, Mercury, Lead, Cadmium and phosphorus are elevated in both herbal drug as stated by (World Health Organization, 2017) permissible limit of heavy metals in drinking water.

Table 6. Relationship between malondialdehyde and some renal function parameters.

	Creatinine		Sodium		Potassium		Malondialdehyde	
	r- value	p-value	r-value	p-value	r-value	p-value	r-value	p-value
Creatinine			0.213	0.317	0.544	0.006*	-0.250	0.238
Sodium	0.213	0.317			0.234	0.271	-0.195	0.362
Potassium	0.544	0.006*	0.234	0.271			-0.203	0.342
Malondialdehyde	-0.250	0.238	-0.195	0.3628	-0.203	0.342		

The result showed a strong positive relationship between potassium and creatinine ($p = 0.006$).

4. DISCUSSION

The findings from this study reveal a concerning level of heavy-metal contamination in locally produced polyherbal cancer remedies and provide experimental evidence of their nephrotoxic potential when administered to animal models. The elevated concentrations of mercury (0.236-0.100 ppm), lead (1.029-0.853 ppm), and cadmium (0.772-0.405 ppm) in both Agbo A and Agbo B formulations notably exceed the World Health Organization’s permissible limits in potable water (0.006, 0.01, and 0.003 ppm, respectively), indicating significant public health risks. These results align with prior reports that herbal formulations especially those produced in unregulated settings often harbor heavy metals derived from environmental uptake, processing contamination, or intentional inclusion for perceived therapeutic potency (He et al., 2020; Luo et al., 2021; Satarug et al., 2024).

The toxicological implications of these findings are particularly significant considering the kidney’s pivotal function in the filtration, accumulation, and excretion of xenobiotics and metal ions. The marked reduction in relative kidney weight observed in rats treated with sorafenib alone and in those receiving combined sorafenib herbal exposures indicates structural or functional compromise, reflecting the early onset of nephrotoxic insult. This observation is in harmony with prior toxicopathological evidence linking heavy-metal exposure to tubular atrophy, mitochondrial injury, and oxidative degeneration of renal tissue (Liu et al., 2021; Lentini et al., 2017). Furthermore, the significant elevation in serum creatinine, together with the strong positive correlation between creatinine and potassium levels, underscores the presence of impaired glomerular filtration and electrolyte dysregulation biochemical hallmarks of progressive renal injury (Santos et al., 2020; Lyrio et al., 2024). The observed rise in malondialdehyde (MDA) level a recognized indicator of lipid peroxidation provides further

confirmation of oxidative stress as a major mediator of renal damage. Heavy metals such as cadmium and lead are potent inducers of reactive oxygen species that overwhelm the antioxidant defense system by depleting glutathione and impairing mitochondrial activity.

These processes ultimately result in cellular membrane injury, loss of ionic integrity, and apoptotic death of renal tubular cells (Tchounwou et al., 2019). The negative correlations recorded between MDA and renal function markers (creatinine, sodium, and potassium) in this study strengthen this mechanistic explanation, implying that heightened oxidative stress undermines renal cellular stability and disrupts electrolyte homeostasis. Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS) profiling of the polyherbal formulations revealed a broad spectrum of phytochemicals with recognized pharmacological potential, including quinazoline derivatives, morphinan alkaloids, and pancracine - compounds associated with anticancer, analgesic, and antioxidant effects. Although these bioactive constituents may partly account for the perceived therapeutic value of the preparations, their coexistence with toxic heavy metals presents a paradox of simultaneous benefit and harm.

Comparable patterns have been documented in Indian Ayurvedic formulations and Nigerian *Agbo* decoctions, where beneficial plant metabolites are frequently accompanied by hazardous contaminants originating from polluted soils or industrial exposure (Onan et al., 2024; Okoro et al., 2023). This duality highlights the urgent need for sustained toxicovigilance within traditional medical systems, especially among vulnerable populations such as cancer patients, whose renal function is often compromised by chemotherapy, dehydration, or disease-related stress. Variations in body weight among treatment groups reflect systemic toxic effects. Rats treated with sorafenib alone showed reduced body weight, indicating drug-related anorexia and hepatic stress, whereas CCl₄ - treated rats gained weight, likely due to inflammation and fluid retention.

These outcomes are consistent with chronic toxicity patterns and suggest that concurrent exposure to chemotherapeutic and herbal agents may amplify systemic harm (Azzam et al., 2014; Lanas et al., 1995). Overall, the study reveals that although polyherbal cancer remedies contain bioactive compounds with therapeutic potential, their benefits are negated by the presence of nephrotoxic metals. Combined exposure to these contaminants can worsen chemotherapy-induced renal injury, accelerating chronic kidney disease. This supports earlier findings that unregulated herbal products contribute to cumulative organ damage (He et al., 2020; Satarug et al., 2024).

Hence, strict regulatory control, quality assurance, and periodic monitoring of herbal formulations are essential. Public sensitization on the dangers of unverified herbal use and further research integrating histopathological and molecular analyses are recommended to clarify mechanisms of heavy-metal-induced nephrotoxicity and improve herbal medicine safety.

5. CONCLUSION

This study confirms that many polyherbal cancer remedies marketed in southeastern Nigeria contain unsafe levels of nephrotoxic heavy metals, notably lead, cadmium, and mercury. Biochemical and oxidative stress markers in Wistar rats indicate that prolonged consumption could impair renal function, especially in cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy. Although GC–MS profiling identified compounds with possible anticancer and

antioxidant properties, their benefits are overshadowed by toxic contamination. These findings highlight the dual nature of such remedies therapeutically promising yet toxicologically hazardous and call for strict quality assurance and toxicological regulation.

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